

A Generic Filter Driver for file Classification in Linux

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Abstract— Whenever, user has to deal with lots of files present in the system, managing and storing these files systematically is very important in order to make it easier to access them. Here comes the role of our FS Filter Driver which helps user to classify these files and check the intrusions in these files and store them in separate directories according to their file extensions. It also classifies the files which are downloaded from the Internet. Thus Driver eases the programmer's job of handling a lot of files by classifying them systematically.

Categories and Subject Descriptors –

E.5 FILES (D.4.3, F.2.2, H.2)-Files Management and sorting and classification, is required for high storage capacity server because it stores large number of files of different types. This Filter is used to sort that files with their types and store this file in separate directory according to their type.

KEYWORDS- VFS; open; write; sys_write; FS

1. INTRODUCTION

File systems often need to evolve and require many changes to support new features. Traditional file-system development is difficult because most of the work is done in the kernel—a hostile development environment where progress is slow, debugging is difficult, and simple mistakes can crash systems. Kernel work also requires deep understanding of system internals, resulting in developers spending a lot of time becoming familiar with the system's details [1, 3, and 12]. Whenever, user has to deal with lots of files present in the system, managing and storing these files systematically is very important in order to make it easier to access them. Here comes the role of our FS Filter Driver which helps user to classify these files and store them in separate directories according to their file extensions. It also classifies the files which are downloaded from the Internet. Thus our product eases the programmer's job of handling a lot of files by classifying them systematically.

The idea of the project was mainly, to provide ease to:

➤ A user by providing a systematic organization of files in the system depending upon their extensions. This allows the user to access the files easily.

➤ A user by reducing his job of specifying the whole path while downloading a file from Internet. Filter Driver module will extract the extension of the file being downloaded and redirect it automatically. Hence, it partially acts like a download manager.

1.2 Similar Tools Available

1.Flashgot

Flashgot is a free Mozilla / Firefox / Flock / Thunderbird extension meant to handle single and massive downloads with several external download managers [4].

2. Aria

Aria for Linux / UNIX downloads the files from the Internet via HTTP / HTTPS or FTP. The transfer can be paused, resumed, queued and saved. It supports CRC / MD5 checking [2,5].

3. DAP (Download Accelerator Plus)

DAP has pre-defined folders for all kinds of categories like – Software / Archives, Music / Sounds etc. where files of that particular category get redirected. And other similar tools are Downloader 4X, Gwget.

2. TYPES OF FILE SYSTEM IN LINUX

Linux includes support for many popular file systems, making it possible to easily access the file systems of other operating systems. This is particularly useful in dual-boot scenarios and when migrating files from one operating system to another. The supported file systems include (but are not limited to):

1. EXT2

Until recently, the ext2 file system had been the standard file system for Linux. As such, it has received extensive testing and is considered one of the more robust file systems in use today. However, there is no perfect file system, and ext2 is no exception. One problem that is commonly reported is that an ext2 file system must undergo a lengthy file system integrity check if the system was not cleanly shut down. While this requirement is not unique to ext2, the popularity of ext2, combined with the advent of larger disk drives, meant that file system integrity checks were taking longer and longer. Something had to be done. The next section describes the approach taken to resolve this issue under Linux [5,6,7].

2. EXT3

The ext3 file system builds upon ext2 by adding journaling capabilities to the already-proven ext2 codebase. As a journaling file system, ext3 always keeps the file system in a consistent state, eliminating the need for lengthy file system integrity checks. This is accomplished by writing all file system changes to an on-disk journal, which is then flushed on a regular basis. After an unexpected system event (such as a power outage or system crash), the only operation that needs to take place prior to making the file system available is to process the contents of the journal; in most cases this takes approximately one second. Because ext3's on-disk data format is based on ext2, it is possible to access an ext3 file system on any system capable of reading and writing an ext2 file system (without the benefit of journaling, however). This can be a sizable benefit in organizations where some systems are using ext3 and some are still using ext2[8].

3. ISO 9660

In 1987, the International Organization for Standardization (known as ISO) released standard 9660. ISO 9660 defines how files are represented on CD-ROMs. Red Hat Linux system administrators will likely see ISO 9660-formatted data in two places:

- CD-ROMs
- Files (usually referred to as *ISO images*) containing complete ISO 9660 file systems, meant to be written to CD-R or CD-RW media.

The basic ISO 9660 standard is rather limited in functionality, especially when compared with more modern file systems. File names may be a maximum of eight characters long and an extension of no more than three characters is permitted. However, various extensions to the standard have become popular over the years, among them:

- Rock Ridge - Uses some fields undefined in ISO 9660 to provide support features such as long mixed-case file names, symbolic links, and nested directories (in other words, directories that can themselves contain other directories)
- Joliet - An extension of the ISO 9660 standard, developed by Microsoft to allow CD-ROMs to contain long file names, using the Unicode character set Linux is able to correctly interpret ISO 9660 file systems using both the Rock Ridge and Joliet extensions.

4. MSDOS

Linux also supports file systems from other operating systems. As the name for the msdos file system implies, the original operating system supporting this file system was Microsoft's MS-DOS. As in MS-DOS, a Red Hat Linux system accessing an msdos file system is limited to 8.3 file names. Likewise, other file attributes such as permissions and ownership cannot be changed. However, from a file interchange standpoint, the msdos file system is more than sufficient to get the job done [9,10].

5. VFAT

The vfat file system was first used by Microsoft's Windows 95 operating system. An improvement over the msdos file system, file names on a vfat file system may be longer than msdos's 8.3. However, permissions and ownership still cannot be changed [11].

6. EXT4

The ext4 or fourth extended file system is a journaling file system for Linux, developed as the successor to ext3. It was born as a series of backward compatible extensions to ext3 meant to extend storage limits and add other performance improvements. However, other Linux kernel developers opposed accepting extensions to ext3 for stability reasons, and proposed to fork the source code of ext3, rename it as ext4, and do all the development there, without affecting the current ext3 users [12].

3. GENERIC FILTER DRIVER

The different **approaches** that were available for implementing the problem statement are

1. Application-level product

There can be a daemon process running at the background, which will monitor all the file transfers.

2. Kernel-level implementation

Here, a Generic Filter Driver can be written in the Linux kernel, which will serve all the File Systems.

3. A separate Driver for File Classification

A separate Filter Driver can be written which is required to be mounted at a particular location in the system.

3.1 Why Kernel Level?

The application level File Classifier is easier to develop and port because it resides outside the kernel. However, its performance is poor due to the extra context switches. It must contend for system resources with all other processes on the system—resources such as memory, swap space, CPU cycles, etc. If the system becomes busy because of normal user activities, the daemon process can get de-scheduled, swapped out, or even killed. The separate Driver needs to be mounted at

the particular location in the system and this mount point decides the File System type[13]. So it becomes File System Specific Driver. The kernel level implementation is considered to be clean as there is no single chance of failure. The implementation of the Filter Driver at the Virtual File System level in the kernel makes it Generic (File System Independent). Thus, the Filter Driver can implement at the Kernel Level in a better fashion[14].

3.2 VFS

The Virtual File System (VFS) is the subsystem of the kernel that implements the file system interface provided to the user - space programs. All file systems rely on the VFS to allow them not only to coexist but also to interoperate between them. This enables the programmers to use standard UNIX system calls to read and write to different file systems on different media.

The Virtual File System plays a major role in our project. All the system calls that are targeted at the original files system pass through the VFS [14, 15, 16]. Our Filter Driver intercepts these calls before reaching the target file system. In this manner the filter driver replaces the original functionality of the underlying file system.

File System Abstraction Layer

A generic interface for any type of file system is only feasible because the kernel itself implements an abstraction layer around its low - level file system interface. This abstraction layer enables Linux to support different File systems, even if they differ greatly in supported features or behavior. This is possible because the VFS provides a common file model that is capable of representing any conceivable file system's general features and behavior. The abstraction layer works by defining the basic abstract interfaces and data structures all file systems support. The file systems mold their view of concepts such as "this is how I open files" and "this is what a directory is to me" to match the expectations of the VFS. The actual file system code hides the implementation details. To the VFS layer and the rest of the kernel, however, each file system looks the same. They all support notions, such as files and directories and operations, such as create file and delete file. The result is a general abstraction layer that enables the kernel to support many types of file systems easily and cleanly. The file systems are programmed to provide the abstracted interfaces and data structures the VFS expects; in turn, the kernel works on any file system and the exported user - space interface seamlessly works on any file system. In fact, nothing in the kernel needs to understand the underlying details of the file systems, except the file systems themselves. For example, consider a simple user - space program that does

```
write (f, &buf, len);
```

This writes the *len* bytes pointed to by *&buf* into the current position in the file represented by the file descriptor *f*. This system call is first handled by a generic *sys_write()* system call that determines the actual file writing method for the file system on which *f* resides[14,15]. The generic write system call then invokes this method, which is part of the file system

implementation, to write the data to the media (or whatever this file system does on write).

Figure 1.VFS - File system Interaction

4. FILTER DRIVER MODULS

This module performs the actual operation of file classification. When a file is to be saved to the system, the 'create' system call is invoked which in turn invokes the 'open' system call [12, 13]. The function implementation of the 'open' system call invokes the Filter Driver module. It intercepts the requests targeted at the underlying File Systems. The Driver gets the pathname of the file to be saved, extracts its extension, constructs a new pathname and re-directs the file to the pre-defined location. In this way, it organizes the files according to their extensions [18, 19].

Figure 2.File Classification operation

4.1. User Interface

User interacts with the Filter Driver with the help of the User Interface module. Through this interface, he can enable or disable the Filter and can view the default destination path and design in gtk+ technology.

Figure 3.Filter Activation Operation

4.2. Proc Interface

Proc Interface module builds an Interface between User space and Kernel space. It creates a file in the Proc FS and writes an OFF to it [16, 20].

Figure 4.Proc Interface Creation

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The aim of the Filter is,

➤ To develop a user-friendly product this systematically organizes files in the system depending upon their extensions. This allows the user to access the files easily.

➤ To reduce user's job of specifying the whole path while downloading a file from Internet. Filter Driver module will extract the extension of the file being downloaded and redirect it automatically.

➤ In future with the help of this Filter Driver we integrate current file system into Secure File System.

This has been successfully done through the various development researches. As mentioned, each component of the this Filter will be constructed after considerable research and study.

And in future we will see that implementing Secure File System in kernel enables the operating system to provide file data security as one of its inherent functionality with the help of this generic driver. SFS is cryptographically enforced and uses public-private pair key to control the access of a file using this Filter Driver. Using public cryptography makes it more reliable, secure and in a way provides user authentication also. The scheme guarantees an end-to-end protection leading to a secure computing environment.

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